

Survey Protocol and Questionnaire

This appendix present the questionnaire applied to the industry practitioners and researchers to collect real data and analysis the current state of the practice problems regarding SoS interoperability and task of interoperability requirements analysis in development of the systems and similar complex system. Figure 44 shows the welcome page the of Survey Anyplace¹ with the partner Fraunhofer IESE, which we used to conducted the online survey.

Figure 44 – Excerpt of the Welcome in the system Survey Anyplace

Source: Elaborated by the author.

SoS Interoperability Requirements Analysis

Welcome

¹ <<https://surveyanyplace.com/>>

Thank you for accepting the invitation to participate in this survey. Your collaboration in this survey is essential to aggregate value to the research on Systems-of-System (SoS) Architecture.

In this survey, the University of São Paulo (ICMC/USP), Brazil, and Fraunhofer IESE, Germany, intend to collect real data regarding SoS interoperability and the task of interoperability requirements analysis in the development of these systems and similar complex systems. Thus, we are consulting experienced industry professionals and researchers to answer some questions about this challenging topic.

Free and Clarified Consent

By clicking on the consent statement and submitting the completed survey, you indicate their willingness to participate. Your participation in this survey is voluntary and you can withdraw at any time; in this case, your data will be discarded.

Survey Data: 1st reminder: July 09, 2018; 2st reminder: July 21, 2018; and **Deadline** August 10, 2018.

Kind regards,

PhD Student Cristiane Lana (University of São Paulo, Brazil; University of Kaiserslautern and Fraunhofer IESE, Germany)

Prof. Dr. Elisa Yumi Nakagawa (University of São Paulo, Brazil)

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Architectural Analysis Practices of SoS Interoperability Requirements

The following definitions apply to the terms used in this survey:

Systems-of-Systems are used to describe large, complex, and software-intensive systems composed of separately developed systems with managerial and operational independence (i.e., constituent systems) that work collaboratively towards the achievement of a global mission.

Interoperability is a requirement that provides dynamic interactive information and the possibility of data exchange among constituent systems to work together to enable new functionalities.

Emergent Behavior is the combination of constituent systems interacting with each other and with the environment over time to create new functionalities.

System Requirements Analysis is a structural process aimed at translating user capability into requirements.

1 - Have you (or your organization) ever performed interoperability requirements analysis for SoS development?*

Figure 45 – Research question one - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

2 - In your opinion, which is(are) the reason(s) why interoperability requirements analysis is not considered in SoS development? Please choose all that apply.

Figure 46 – Research question two - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

3 - In your opinion, who should perform the task of interoperability requirements analysis?* Please chose all that apply.

Figure 47 – Research question three - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

4 - In your experience, which are the main tasks that deal with interoperability requirement analysis?* Please all that apply.

Figure 48 – Research question four - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

5 - Which formal level has been used to document interoperability requirements of SoS in projects (or organizations) in which you have been involved?* Please all that apply.

The screenshot shows a survey question in a web browser. The question is: "5 - Which formal level has been used to document interoperability requirements of SoS in projects (or organizations) in which you have been involved?*" Below the question, it says "Please all that apply". There are five radio button options: "Formal specification (e.g., RSML, Z language, KAOS)", "Natural language, please provide an example", "Semi-formal specification (e.g., UML, SysML, FUML)", "Structured (e.g., table)", and "Other, please specify". Below these options is a text input field with the placeholder "Please, specify your answer or provide an example here:". At the bottom of the form is a green "NEXT" button.

Figure 49 – Research question five - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

6 - In your experience, which of the following languages support the specification of SoS interoperability requirements?* Please choose all that apply.

The screenshot shows a survey question in a web browser. The question is: "6 - In your experience, which of the following languages support the specification of SoS interoperability requirements?*" Below the question, it says "Please choose all that apply". There are ten radio button options: "Domain-Specific Modeling Languages", "KAOS Methodology", "Prototype Verification Systems", "Requirements State Machine Language", "Statecharts", "SysML", "UML", "Timed Communication Sequential Process Timed", "Web Service Description Language - WSDL", and "Other, please specify". Below these options is a text input field with the placeholder "Please, specify or comments your answer here:". At the bottom of the form is a green "NEXT" button.

Figure 50 – Research question six - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

7 - Considering the SoS development lifecycle, in which activities have you elicited interoperability requirements in projects (or organizations) in which you have been involved?*
Please all that apply

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a survey question. The question is: "7 - Considering the SoS development lifecycle, in which activities have you elicited interoperability requirements in projects (or organizations) in which you have been involved?*" Below the question, it says "Please all that apply". There is a list of activities with radio buttons: Architectural analysis, Architectural evaluation, Architectural synthesis, Implementation, Requirements analysis, Requirements elicitation, Requirements specification, Execution, and Other, please specify. Below the list is a text input field for comments and a "NEXT" button.

Figure 51 – Research question seven - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

8 - In your experience, how much effort (%) has been spent in the SoS Requirements Engineering phase on eliciting interoperability requirements?* Please choose only one of the following.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a survey question. The question is: "8 - In your experience, how much effort (%) has been spent in the SoS Requirements Engineering phase on eliciting interoperability requirements?*" Below the question, it says "Please choose only one of the following". There is a list of effort percentages with radio buttons: <10%, 11% to 30%, 31% to 50%, 51% to 70%, 71% to 90%, and > 90%. Below the list is a text input field for comments and a "NEXT" button.

Figure 52 – Research question eight - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

9 - In your experience, what has been the abstraction level of the interoperability requirements elicited in the SoS Requirements Engineering phase?*

The image shows a survey question displayed over a background image of a modern building. The question is: "9 - In your experience, what has been the abstraction level of the interoperability requirements elicited in the SoS Requirements Engineering phase? *". Below the question are five radio button options: "Low abstraction", "Moderate abstraction", "Neutral", "High abstraction", and "Very high abstraction". There is also a "Comments:" field and a "NEXT" button.

Figure 53 – Research question nine - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

10 - In your experience regarding SoS architectural analysis, how much effort (%) has been spent on eliciting interoperability requirements?* Please choose only one of the following.

The image shows a survey question displayed over a background image of a modern building. The question is: "10 - In your experience regarding SoS architectural analysis, how much effort (%) has been spent on eliciting interoperability requirements? *". Below the question is the instruction "Please choose only one of the following" and five radio button options: "<10%", "11% to 30%", "31% to 50%", "51% to 70%", and "71% to 90%". There is also a "> 90%" option, a "Comments:" field, and a "NEXT" button.

Figure 54 – Research question ten - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

11 - In your experience, what has been the abstraction level of the interoperability requirements elicited in the SoS Architectural Analysis phase?*

11 - In your experience, what has been the abstraction level of the interoperability requirements elicited in the SoS Architectural Analysis phase? *

- Low abstraction
- Moderate abstraction
- Neutral
- High abstraction
- Very high abstraction

Comments:

NEXT

Figure 55 – Research question 11 - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

12 - In your opinion, which SoS characteristics impact SoS interoperability requirements?*

12 - In your opinion, which SoS characteristics impact SoS interoperability requirements?*

- Emergent behavior of the SoS
- Evolutionary development of SoS
- Distribution of the constituent systems
- Operational and managerial independence of the constituent systems
- Collaboration between constituent systems
- Open-ended architecture of the SoS
- Heterogeneity of the constituent systems
- Mission of the SoS
- Mission of the constituent systems
- Adaptability of the SoS
- Other, please specify

Please, specify or comments your answer here:

NEXT

Figure 56 – Research question 12 - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

13 - In your opinion, which are the main challenges/difficulties regarding the analysis of interoperability requirements?* Please choose all that apply.

13 - In your opinion, which are the main challenges/difficulties regarding the analysis of interoperability requirements? *

Please choose all that apply

- Lack of automated technological support
- Lack of methodological support (e.g., process, methods, and methodologies)
- Lack of support for inter-artifact and intra-artifact traceability
- Lack of guidelines for the interoperability analysis
- Lack of best practices for practitioners
- Lack of a unified taxonomy
- Lack of a specific language for specifying interoperability requirements

Other, please specify

If possible, please comment:

Figure 57 – Research question 13 i- Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

14 - Have interoperability requirements been represented in the architectural views of the SoS?* Please all that apply.

14 - Have interoperability requirements been represented in the architectural views of the SoS? *

Please all that apply

- Capability
- Functional
- Implementation
- Logical
- Operational
- System
- Technical

Other, please specify

Please, specify your answer here:

Figure 58 – Research question 14 - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

15 - How did the architect/engineer solve issues related to uncovered interoperability requirements?*

Figure 59 – Research question 15 - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

16 - In your experience, do you consider interoperability as a ...*

Figure 60 – Research question 16 - Architectural Analysis Practices

Source: Elaborated by the author.

Landscape regarding SoS interoperability

It would be amazing for us to continue hearing your opinions and learning from your experience!
We are almost done!

16 - Which development methodologies have been applied in SoS projects in which you have been involved?* Please choose all that apply.

The screenshot shows a survey window titled "Landscape regarding SoS interoperability" overlaid on a background image of a modern building. The text inside the window reads: "It would be amazing for us to continue hearing your opinions and learning from your experience! We are almost done!". Below this is question 16: "16 - Which development methodologies have been applied in SoS projects in which you have been involved? *". The instruction "Please choose all that apply" is followed by a list of radio button options: "Ad hoc", "Agile; please specify", "Rational Unified Process", "Waterfall-based; please specify", and "Other; please specify". There is also a text input field for "Please specify or comment your answer here" and a "NEXT" button at the bottom right.

Figure 61 – Research question 16 - SoS interoperability

Source: Elaborated by the author.

17 - Have you been using any framework to support the development of SoS?* Please choose all that apply.

The screenshot shows a survey window titled "17 - Have you been using any framework to support the development of SoS? *". The instruction "Please choose all that apply" is followed by a list of radio button options: "Department of Defense Architecture Framework – DoDAF", "Flexible and Intelligent Learning Architecture Framework for SoS – FILA – SoS", "Ministry of Defence Architecture Framework (MODAF)", "NATO Architecture Framework - NAF", "Open Group Architecture Framework – TOGAF", "SoSE Hierarchical Framework", "Zachman Framework", "I do not use any framework", and "Other; please specify". There is also a text input field for "Please specify or comment your answer here" and a "NEXT" button at the bottom right.

Figure 62 – Research question 17 - SoS interoperability

Source: Elaborated by the author.

18 - Do you have experience with SoS interoperability in any of the following application domains?* Please choose all that apply.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a survey question. The question is: "18 - Do you have experience with SoS interoperability in any of the following application domains?*" with the instruction "Please choose all that apply". Below the question is a list of application domains, each with a radio button: Aerospace, Airport, Autonomous Vehicles, Avionics, Defense, eHealth, Ecosystems, Naval, Railway, Smart Home, Telecommunication, and Other, please specify. At the bottom of the list is a text input field labeled "Please specify or comment your" and a "NEXT" button.

Figure 63 – Research question 18 - SoS interoperability

Source: Elaborated by the author.

19 - Which type of SoS interoperability has been used in projects (or organizations) in which you have been involved?* Please choose all that apply

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a survey question. The question is: "19 - Which type of SoS interoperability has been used in projects (or organizations) in which you have been involved?*" with the instruction "Please choose all that apply". Below the question is a list of types of interoperability, each with a radio button: Interoperability concerning the meaningful abstraction of reality using models and simulation; Interoperability among the organizations that are responsible for SoS construction and maintenance; Interoperability concerning the relationships within and between enterprises, business relationships, and legal relationships; Interoperability as achieved when the inter-operating systems are aware of the methods and procedures employed by each system; Interoperability concerning the meaning of exchanged information; Interoperability as related to data formats and consistency, and how such data have been transmitted; Interoperability as related to the infrastructure necessary for linking computer systems and services; and Other, please specify. At the bottom of the list is a text input field labeled "Comments:" and a "NEXT" button.

Figure 64 – Research question 19 - SoS interoperability

Source: Elaborated by the author.

20 - In particular, based on your experience, which type of interoperability is/should be considered most relevant during the architectural analysis of SoS?* Please choose all that apply.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a survey question. The question is: "20 - In particular, based on your experience, which type of interoperability is/should be considered most relevant during the architectural analysis of SoS?*" Below the question, it says "Please choose all that apply". There are eight radio button options:

- Interoperability concerning the meaningful abstraction of reality using models and simulation
- Interoperability among the organizations that are responsible for SoS construction and maintenance
- Interoperability concerning the relationships within and between enterprises, business relationships, and legal relationships
- Interoperability as achieved when the interoperating systems are aware of the methods and procedures employed by each system
- Interoperability concerning the meaning of exchanged information
- Interoperability as related to data formats and consistency, and how such data have been transmitted
- Interoperability as related to the infrastructure necessary for linking computer systems and services
- Other, please specify

 Below the options is a "Comments:" field and a "NEXT" button. The background of the survey is a photograph of a modern building with a glass facade.

Figure 65 – Research question 20 - SoS interoperability

Source: Elaborated by the author.

21 - Which model have you been applying to evaluate SoS interoperability?* Please choose all that apply.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a survey question. The question is: "21 - Which model have you been applying to evaluate SoS interoperability?*" Below the question, it says "Please choose all that apply". There are ten radio button options:

- Spectrum of Interoperability Model (SoIM)
- Quantification of Interoperability Methodology (QoIM)
- Military Communications and Information Systems Interoperability (MCIS)
- Levels of Information System Interoperability Model (LISI)
- Organizational Interoperability Maturity Model for C2 (OIM)
- Levels of Conceptual Interoperability Model (LCIM)
- Layers of Coalition Interoperability (LCI)
- NATO C3 Technical Architecture Reference Model for Interoperability (NMI)
- Organizational Interoperability Agility Model (DIAM)
- Layered Interoperability Score (i-Score)
- System-of-Systems Interoperability Model (SoSI)
- I do not use any model
- Other, please specify

 Below the options is a "Comments:" field and a "NEXT" button. The background of the survey is a photograph of a modern building with a glass facade.

Figure 66 – Research question 21 - SoS interoperability

Source: Elaborated by the author.

Please feel free to provide any information or send by email any file that you consider useful for this survey.

Demographic data

1- What is your country of residence?*

A screenshot of a web browser displaying a survey question. The browser's address bar shows 's.surveyanyplace.com/tu/14ourProfessions'. The survey progress indicator at the top right shows '25/31'. The background image is a modern building with 'Fraunhofer' signage. A dark grey overlay box contains the text 'Demographic data:' followed by the question '1- What is your country of residence?*' and a text input field. A green 'NEXT' button is positioned at the bottom of the overlay.

Figure 67 – Demographic research question one

Source: Elaborated by the author.

2 - What is your current occupation/career?*

 Please choose only one of the following.A screenshot of a web browser displaying a survey question. The browser's address bar shows 's.surveyanyplace.com/tu/14ourProfessions'. The survey progress indicator at the top right shows '26/31'. The background image is the same modern building as in Figure 67. A dark grey overlay box contains the text '2 - What is your current occupation/career?*' followed by 'Please choose only one of the following'. Below this are five radio button options: 'Researcher', 'SoS Architect', 'Interoperability Engineer', 'Domain Analyst', and 'Other; please specify'. There is a text input field for the 'Other' option. Below the options is the text 'Please; specify or comments your answer here:'. A green 'NEXT' button is positioned at the bottom of the overlay.

Figure 68 – Demographic research question two

Source: Elaborated by the author.

3 - How many years have you been working in this position?* Please specify.

A screenshot of a web browser displaying a survey question. The browser's address bar shows 's.surveyplace.com/fraunhoferinterac'. The question is '3 - How many years have you been working in this position?*' with the instruction 'Please specify'. Below the question is a large, empty text input field. At the bottom of the question box is a green 'NEXT' button. The background of the survey is a photograph of a modern building with 'Fraunhofer' signage.

Figure 69 – Demographic research question three

Source: Elaborated by the author.

4 - What is your educational degree?* Please choose only one of the following.

A screenshot of a web browser displaying a survey question. The browser's address bar shows 's.surveyplace.com/fraunhoferinterac'. The question is '4 - What is your educational degree?*' with the instruction 'Please choose only one of the following'. Below the question is a list of radio button options: 'Technologist degree', 'Bachelor degree', 'Master student', 'Master degree', 'PhD student', 'PhD degree', and 'Other, please specify'. There is a text input field for the 'Other' option. At the bottom of the question box is a green 'NEXT' button. The background of the survey is a photograph of a modern building with 'Fraunhofer' signage.

Figure 70 – Demographic research question four

Source: Elaborated by the author.

Thank you for your willingness to help us! If you are interested in the results of this survey, just write your email address in this field. We will then contact you as soon as we finish this survey.

Sincerely,

PhD Student Cristiane Lana (University of São Paulo, Brazil; University of Kaiserslautern and Fraunhofer IESE, Germany)

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